

Research report: “Exploring the annotation scope and process in the PARSEME-GRC corpus: practicalities of annotating across sentence boundaries and in verse”, Short-Term Scientific Mission, Cambridge University, UK (21–27/09/2025).

Funding: This work received support from the CA21167 COST action UniDive, funded by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

The distribution of Verbal multi-word expressions in Ancient Greek: from token distance to genre-driven selection criteria

Elena Squeri

Sapienza – University of Rome (elena.squeri@uniroma1.it)

1. Token distance of constituting elements of verbal multi-word expressions (VMWEs)

A preliminary assessment of the token distance among the furthest constituting elements of VMWEs in Xenophon’s *Anabasis* 1-4, achieved by running a dedicated script¹ over the annotated text published in the first release of the PARSEME-GRC corpus², has given the following results.

Most MWEs fall between about 2 and 10 tokens but we can acknowledge a variation in the numbers of each category. Non causative light verb constructions (LVCs) and Multi-verb constructions (MVCs) are the ones displaying the shortest range, never extending over more than 10 tokens, with an average distance of 3-4 tokens (on the token distance of the constituting elements of LVCs in literary Attic Greek, see also Fendel 2025 § 3.1.1). Oddly, the VMWE category displaying the highest

¹ The data and the graphic report were extracted and elaborated thanks to the technical support of Dr. Paraskevi Platanou.

² The annotated text is the one from Marchant (1904), available in Open Access on the Perseus catalog (<https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3atext%3a1999.01.0201>).

degree of token distance (both in absolute terms and in the middle value) and the widest fluctuation in length is the one of Verbal Idioms (VIDs). This might be due to the variability of VIDs in terms of the number of their constituting elements, but contrasts with the idea of (verbal) idioms being the VMWEs whose behaviour deviates the most from the one of expressions building their meaning in syntax (see Mel'čuk 2023, chap. 4 on idioms and their potential syntactic discontinuity).

These data can also be confronted with some preliminary ones drawn from the annotation of the VIDs by V. B. Fendel (forthcoming)³:

- [διά + NOUN (GEN, eventive) + VP (intransitive, movement)]
- [εἰς (οὗτος / ὅδε / τοσοῦτος / τοιοῦτος / τοςόσδε / τοιόσδε) + NOUN (GEN/ACC, eventive) + VP (intransitive, movement)]

in the corpus of attic tragedy (all the tragedies of Aeschylus, Sophocles and Euripides)⁴, which shows that they are never diffused over more than 5 tokens. This perfectly displays how variation can happen both among VMWEs and within VMWEs categories. This especially concerns categories as VIDs, which, with the exception of the verbal head, can have constituting elements, with different constraints with reference to their obligatory adjacency. In the mentioned VID clusters, built with a PP, only modifiers and determiners linked to the nominal element of the PP can intervene between the particle and the noun itself. Moreover, the varying transitivity of verbs heading VIDs impact the possibility of lexical material intervening between the verb and the other constituting elements of the idiom: in the aforementioned examples, the involvement of intransitive motion verbs prevents any argument intervening between the verb and the PP.

2. Genre-driven use of VMWEs: pragmatics, information structure and discourse cohesion

What observed in the previous paragraph must also be connected to the fact that, with the exception of prepositives, postpositives (Dover 1960, 12-19) and clitics, which are subject to Wackernagel's law (1892), the positioning of verbs, nouns with argument/subject role, and full PPs in Ancient Greek sentences is influenced by information structure criteria (Dik 1995; 2007; Matić 2003; Celano 2013a; 2013b) rather than by a predetermined word-order. Some studies have also argued that Ancient Greek is a non-configurational language (Luraghi 2010). This aspect interacts with the structuring and the token distance of the constituting elements of VMWEs (see Fendel 2025, chap. 6–7 on LVCs), which can be exploited for different pragmatic purposes.

³ Paper presented at the workshop 'Kicking the metaphorical bucket? Verbal multi-word expressions in verse', held within 'The 17th International Conference of Greek Linguistics' (ICGL: <https://icgl17.mml.cam.ac.uk/>).

⁴ Editions: Murray 1960 & Page 1972 for Aeschylus; Dain–Mazon 1967 for Sophocles; Murray 1966 for Euripides.

A test on the elements intervening between the constituting part of a verb–argument based VMWE was undertaken on the Ancient Greek specific category of formally related Cognate object constructions (‘sing a song’, Lys. 1.45: κίνδυνον ἐκινδύνευον ‘I ran a risk’, on whose interpretation as VMWEs see Squeri 2026; Fendel–Platanou–Squeri 2026). The available data from Lysias’ tribunal speeches annotated in the PARSEME-GRC corpus was then compared to a personal annotation of the same structure in the verse tragic trilogy of Aeschylus’ *Oresteia*⁵. In Lysias more than the 75% of the structures display a direct adjacency of verb and object, whereas in Aeschylus this happens only in 60% of the cases. In Lysias, however, in 60% of cases, the cognate object is combined with a determiner, which very often precedes the cognate object, leaving it adjacent to the verb. In Aeschylus, on the other hand, the cognate object is often left unmodified or combined with a modifier rather than with a determiner. This can be explained by the pragmatic necessities of the two types of text. In Lysias, the structure was exploited for enhancing discourse-cohesion and effectiveness. By offering the nominal part of the structure as a head for a determiner, the speaker would be able to easily recall events known by the audience or already described in its argumentative speech while exposing the case. In Aeschylus, on the other hand, the two constituting elements tend to be used to create a focussed field, in which to include other material, as shown by the tendency of positioning the CO in the first or the last position of the verb.

We also expect the progressive reduction of the degree of freedom in word order in Greek (Taylor 1994; Lavidas 2010) to have had an impact on the positioning of the constituting elements of VMWEs, and, thus, on the use of VMWEs as tools for structuring the information of the sentences. This possibility, however, could only be tested by extending our corpus on the diachronic axis.

3. Genre-driven use of VMWE: stylistic factors

We saw how, in synchrony, different genres may have different pragmatic needs, something which corresponds to a different structuring of the constituting elements of VMWEs. Stylistic needs, however, might also explain the frequency peaks of certain groups or subgroups of VMWEs in certain groups of texts and some variations in their meaning (see e.g. Squeri 2024 on LVCs).

VMWEs as Cognate object constructions, when they involve an object etymologically linked to the head verb (*figurae etymologicae*), can easily produce a strong sound effect, other than being marked by their semantic redundancy (Bruno 2011; Horrocks–Stavrou 2010; Jones 1988; Mirto 2007; Quirk et al. 1985). In the prose texts annotated in the PARSEME-GRC corpus, the author/genre showing the highest occurrence of such a structure is Lysias’ tribunal speeches (1,8 structures/1000 words), followed by Plato’s dialogue in the *Republic* (0,9 structures/1000 words) and Xenophon’s chronicle

⁵ Edition Page 1972.

in the *Anabasis* (0,16 structures/1000 words). Differently from what an interpretation of this structure as a sound rhetorical device might suggest, a personal annotation of Aeschylus' *Oresteia* suggested that tragic verse uses *figurae etymologicae* less than rhetoric prose (0,7 structures/1000 words). The distribution of such structures within the trilogy shows a peak in the *Eumenides*, which confirms the perception of COCs and *figurae etymologicae* as typical of argumentative tribunal speeches. The whole plot of the *Eumenides* is indeed centred around a fictive trial.

An annotation of the whole corpus of Classic tragedy (Fendel, forthcoming) for the VID involving the PPs mentioned in § 1, shows a strong preference for pathological nouns as the nominal element of the PP, which might suggest a link to medical prose (on the involvement of medical language in tragedy, see Miller 1944, Collinge 1962, Guardasole 2000, Jouanna 2012). Tronci (forthcoming) also suggested a shift in the meaning of ἔχθω when heading VMWEs involving names of objects and the expression ἐν χερσὶ(v) in Homeric epic.

4. Implementing verse text in the PARSEME-GRC corpus

The influence that genre, style and pragmatic factors have in the selection and in the internal organisation of Ancient Greek VMWEs suggests that the expansion of the PARSEME-GRC corpus towards tverse texts might be of interest. This would also allow to positively or negatively test the influence of metrical constraints on the internal structuring of VMWEs.

5. Bibliography

- Bruno, C. (2011). When Stylistics Is a Matter of Syntax: Cognate Accusatives in Ancient Greek. In Krisch, T., Lindner, T. (Eds), *Indogermanistik Und Linguistik Im Dialog. Akten Der XIII Fachtagung Der Indogermanischen Gesellschaft Vom 21. Bis 27. September 2008 in Salzburg, Wiesbaden*, 100-109.
- Celano, G. G. A. (2013a). Argument–focus and predicate–focus structure in Ancient Greek: word order and phonology. *Studies in Language* 37(2), 241-266.
- Celano, G. G. A. (2013b). Word Order. In Giannakis G. K. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics Online*, Brill.
- Clary, T. (2007). «Restrictions on the use of the *Figura Etymologica* in Ancient Greek Epic». In Jones-Bley, K., Huld, M.E., Della Volpe, A., Robbins Dexter, M. (Eds), *Proceedings of the 19th Annual UCLA Indo-European Conference*, 113–136.
- Collinge, N. E. (1962). Medical Terms and Clinical Attitudes in the Tragedians. *Bulletin of the Institute of Classical Studies* 9, 43-55.
- Dain, A.–Mazon, P. (1967) (Ed)², *Sophocle*, Voll. 1–3, Paris.
- Dik, H. J. M. (1995), *Word order in Ancient Greek. A pragmatic account of word order variation in Herodotus*, Amsterdam.
- Dik, H. J. M. (2007), *Word Order in Greek Tragic Dialogue*, Oxford–New York.
- Dover, K. J. 1960. *Greek word order*. Cambridge.

- Fendel, V. B. (2025). *Giving Gifts and doing Favours. Literary Classical Attic Greek Support-Verb Constructions*, Leiden.
- Fendel, V. B. (forthcoming). The Verbal Idiom (VID) frame $\delta\acute{\iota}\alpha$ X[GEN] $\epsilon\acute{\iota}\mu\iota$ in the tragedians and beyond. Paper given the 17th International Conference of Greek Linguistics.
- Fendel, V. B.–Platanou, P.–Squeri, E. (2026). Let's square a circle: The PARSEME-GRC corpus of verbal multi-word expressions. *Journal of Greek Linguistics*.
- Guardasole, A. (2000), *Tragedia e medicina nell'Atene del V secolo a.C.*, Napoli.
- Horrocks, G.–Stavrou, M. (2010), Morphological Aspect and the Function and Distribution of Cognate Objects Across Languages. In Rappaport Hovav, M., Doron, E. and Sichel, I. (Eds), *Lexical Semantics, Syntax, and Event Structure*, Oxford–New York, 284-308.
- Jones, M. A. (1988). Cognate Objects and the Case-Filter. *Journal of Linguistics* 24(1), 89-110.
- Jouanna, J. (2012), *Greek Medicine from Hippocrates to Galen: Selected Papers*, Leiden.
- Lavidas, N. (2015). How does a basic word order become ungrammatical? SOV from Classical to Koiné Greek. *Studies in Greek Linguistics* 35, 323-335.
- Luraghi, S. (2010), The rise (and possible downfall) of configurationality. In Luraghi, S., Bubenik, V. (Eds), *The Continuum Companion to Historical Linguistics*, London–New York, 212–229.
- Marchant, E. C. (1903) (Ed.), *Xenophontis opera omnia*, Vol. 3, *Expeditio Cyri*, recognovit, brevisque adnotatione critica instruxit, Londini–Novi Eboraci.
- Matić, D. (2003). Topic, Focus and Discourse Structure. Ancient Greek Word Order. *Studies in Language* 27(3), 573–633.
- Mel'čuk, I. (2023), *General Phraseology. Theory and Practice*, Amsterdam–Philadelphia.
- Miller, H. (1944). Medical Terminology in Tragedy. *Transactions of the American Philological Association* 75, 156–167.
- Mirto, I. M. (2007), Dream a Little Dream of Me. In Camugli, C., Constant, M. and Dister, A. (Eds), *Actes du 26e Colloque international Lexique Grammaire*, 121-128.
- Murray, G. (1955) (Ed.)², *Aeschyli septem quae supersunt tragoediae*, recensuit, Londini–Novi Eboraci.
- Murray, G. (1966), *Euripidis*, Voll. 1–3, recognovit brevisque adnotatione critica instruxit, Londini–Novi Eboraci.
- Page, D. L. (1972) (Ed.), *Aeschyli Septem Quae Supersunt Tragoedias*, Londini–Novi Eboraci.
- Quirk, R. et al. (1985), *A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*, London–New York.
- Squeri, E. (2024), $\chi\rho\acute{\alpha}\omicron\mu\alpha\iota$ as a support verb in the medical jargon of the Hippocratic corpus. In Fendel, V. B. (Ed.), *Support-verb constructions in the corpora of Greek: Between lexicon and grammar?* Berlin, 133–164.
- Squeri, E. (2026). Ancient Greek Cognate object constructions as an instance of complex predication. *Studi e saggi linguistici*.
- Taylor, A. (1994). The Change from SOV to SVO in Ancient Greek. *Language Variation and Change* 6, 1–37.
- Tronci, L. (forthcoming), When 'to have' goes beyond possession. Metaphorical multiword expressions with $\epsilon\chi\epsilon\iota\nu$ in Homer and Classical Drama. Paper presented the 17th International conference of Greek Linguistics.
- Wackernagel, J. (1892), Über ein Gesetz der indogermanischen Wortstellung. *Indogermanische Forschungen* 1, 333-436.